

Diversity-Aware Multi-Party Cloud Services for Human-Robot Interaction

Lucrezia Grassi¹, Danilo Canepa¹, Amy Bellitto^{1,2}, Maura Casadio¹, Antonino Massone², Carmine Tommaso Recchiuto¹, and Antonio Sgorbissa¹

Abstract—This extended abstract summarizes our recent studies in social robotics, showcasing the role of CAIR: an innovative cloud system for autonomous interaction. The system can be easily integrated into artificial agents, providing them with advanced conversational capabilities. The design of CAIR enables personalized engagement, giving rise to the concept of “diversity-aware” robots. Furthermore, the system incorporates control policies that enable robots to moderate group conversations, dynamically allocate attention, and promote inclusivity.

Index Terms—Cloud Robotics, Diversity-Aware Social Robots, Multi-Party Interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, cloud technologies have gained prominence in enhancing the efficiency of intelligent systems and devices. Cloud robotics, defined as the use of remote computing resources to enhance robotic applications, offers advantages such as increased memory, computational power, collective learning, and interconnectivity [1]. As the robotics market experiences exponential growth, especially with the rise of low-cost robots, cloud-based solutions become vital.

While Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) like Pepper and home assistants like Google Home demonstrate promising capabilities, they still have limitations, particularly in scenarios requiring extensive interactions, such as providing support to the elderly, hospitalized individuals, or school children. To tackle these limitations, the CAIR cloud system was developed during the last three years by some of the authors [2]. This system was purposefully designed to facilitate sustainable, knowledge-grounded autonomous interactions between humans and robots. The ability of CAIR to understand users’ intentions and engage in culturally sensitive dialogues is founded on an ontology-based framework for cultural knowledge representation [3].

The CARESSES project¹ pioneered culturally competent SARs for elderly care [4]. Our objective was to take the concept of cultural competence further by introducing into CAIR the idea of “diversity awareness”. This broader concept goes beyond just culture and considers other factors like age, gender, and health status, adapting the robots’ interactions to the unique characteristics of individuals [5]. Achieving

¹L. Grassi, D. Canepa, A. Bellitto, M. Casadio, C. T. Recchiuto, and A. Sgorbissa are with the DIBRIS department, University of Genoa, Via all’Opera Pia 13, 16145 Genoa, Italy.

²A. Massone and A. Bellitto are with the Spinal Cord Unit, Santa Corona Hospital, Viale 25 Aprile 38, 17027 Pietra Ligure, Savona, Italy

Corresponding author’s email: lucrezia.grassi@edu.unige.it

¹www.caressesrobot.org

Fig. 1. CAIR system architecture

this objective required adjustments to the ontology, enabling dialogues to be tailored to individual characteristics.

Another critical aspect is the deployment of social robots in group conversations. With the increasing demand for robots to be part of discussions in various contexts, such as educational settings, healthcare, and social events, ensuring effective participation becomes crucial. For this reason, CAIR has also been designed to empower robots to moderate group conversations. This involves using different control policies, developed to maintain a balance in participation and ensuring that they feel part of a cohesive group [6].

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The CAIR cloud system architecture, depicted in Figure 1, comprises a set of web services, including the Hub, the Dialogue Manager, and the Plan Manager. The Hub service manages incoming requests and directs them to the other services that handle conversation topics and user intents for actions, respectively. The system’s design allows it to provide contextually appropriate responses and plans using the information contained in the knowledge base.

Clients communicate with the server using REST APIs, providing user sentences, and dialogue state information. The dialogue state contains historical information, such as discussed topics, user preferences, and previous sentences. To support multi-party interactions, a Registration service and an Audio Recorder service are introduced. The Registration service enrolls users by capturing their voice and assigning unique profile IDs. The Audio Recorder service transcribes and identifies speakers’ voices. Furthermore, the dialogue state was expanded to include statistics about speakers and their contributions to multi-party interactions.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To evaluate the potential for diversity-aware robots, a study was conducted at Santa Corona Hospital in Pietra Ligure involving 10 clinicians and 10 individuals with Spinal Cord Injuries (SCI) [7]. The interactions took place with the NAO robot from SoftBank robotics, and video footage of these interactions can be viewed on YouTube². Figure 2 (left) shows the interaction between the robot and a hospitalized person. Clinicians participated in a supervised 30-minute dialogue with the NAO robot, guided by a researcher. People with SCI engaged in a 30-minute supervised conversation, followed by an unsupervised phase where the NAO robot was brought to their wards for two hours, enabling unrestricted interaction.

Two hypotheses guided the study: (i) individuals with SCI would exhibit greater acceptance of the robot compared to healthcare professionals, (ii) acceptance among individuals with SCI would remain consistent after a subsequent interaction with the robot, following an initial encounter.

By statistically analyzing the results obtained from the questionnaires, based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), we found that during the 30-minute interaction, people with SCI reported lower anxiety and higher enjoyment levels than clinicians. This divergence might be attributed to the fact that our target population comprises people with SCI, potentially influencing clinicians' assessments since the system was not primarily designed for them. This underscores the importance of diversity-aware robots and validates our first hypothesis. Furthermore, people with SCI experienced reduced anxiety during the 2-hour interaction compared to the 30-minute session. No significant variations were observed in other aspects between these two interaction times, suggesting that perceptions of the robot remained consistent, even though the novelty effect had decreased over time. This outcome affirms our second hypothesis.

To assess the multi-party capabilities of the CAIR system, experiments were conducted at the "Parini-Merello" middle school in Genoa. During the experiments, the humanoid robot Pepper, connected to the CAIR cloud, interacted with groups of four students, as shown in Figure 2 (right). A total of 300 students were divided into 75 groups. These groups participated in experiments where the robot acted as a moderator, employing one of the four developed policies, (i) Balancing hard (BH), (ii) Balancing soft (BS), (iii) Community hard (CH), and (iv) Community soft (CS), and a Neutral policy (N) as a baseline. The control policy (N) had no specific expectations since the robot remained neutral. The Balancing policies (BH and BS) aimed to balance participation in terms of speaking time and the number of words. The Community policies (CH and CS) aimed to reduce the number of participant subgroups. The hard version of the policies involves the robot ignoring responses from unintended users and repeating the question to the intended person. In the soft version, if an unintended user responds, the robot acknowledges their response, replies to them, and then goes back to addressing the intended person

Fig. 2. Left: Diversity-aware interaction between NAO and a person with SCI at the Santa Corona Hospital in Pietra Ligure. Right: Multi-party interaction between the humanoid robot Pepper and a group of four students of the Parini-Merello middle school in Genoa, during an experiment.

for the previous question. A video of the experiments, showing the difference between the policies, is available on YouTube³

Participants registered their voices so that the robot could recognize them, and engaged in a 15-minute interaction with the robot, guided by the chosen policy. They were not informed of the policy beforehand to ensure natural interactions. The experiments lasted about 30 minutes each, including registration, interaction, and the filling of a questionnaire. During these experiments, the robot collected quantitative data to analyze the level of participation among the individuals, to identify distinct subgroups (i.e., communities) of participants, and to evaluate the overall dynamics of the conversation.

The results demonstrated that the policies effectively controlled group conversation dynamics as intended. Statistical comparisons between Balancing (BH and BS) and the Neutral policy (N) showed significant differences, confirming our first hypothesis that the Balancing policy can balance the participation of speakers in terms of speaking time and number of words. Our second hypothesis about the Community policy being able to reduce subgroups was also confirmed, with comparisons between the average number of communities in CH and CS against N yielding significant results.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Wan, S. Tang, H. Yan, D. Li, S. Wang, and A. V. Vasilakos. Cloud robotics: Current status and open issues. *IEEE Access*, 4:2797–2807, 2016.
- [2] L. Grassi, C. T. Recchiuto, and A. Sgorbissa. Sustainable cloud services for verbal interaction with embodied agents. *Intell. Serv. Robot.*, 2023. Accepted for publication.
- [3] L. Grassi, C. T. Recchiuto, and A. Sgorbissa. Knowledge-grounded dialogue flow management for social robots and conversational agents. *Int. J. Soc. Robot.*, 14(5):1273–1293, 2022.
- [4] European Commission. The world's first culturally sensitive robots for elderly care. <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/124441>, 2018. Online; accessed 16 March 2023.
- [5] C.T. Recchiuto and A. Sgorbissa. Diversity-aware social robots meet people: beyond context-aware embodied ai. In *Anthropology, AI and the Future of Human Society*, 2022.
- [6] L. Grassi, C.T. Recchiuto, and A. Sgorbissa. Robot-induced group conversation dynamics: A model to balance participation and unify communities. In *Proc. IEEE IROS 2023*, Detroit, USA, 2023.
- [7] L. Grassi, D. Canepa, A. Bellitto, M. Casadio, A. Massone, C.T. Recchiuto, and A. Sgorbissa. Diversity-aware verbal interaction between a robot and people with spinal cord injury. In *Proc. IEEE RO-MAN 2023*, Busan, South Korea, 2023.

²<https://youtu.be/m22yRiR6JpQ>

³<https://youtu.be/27YvsH7IoSA>